

STRESS RELAXATION BEHAVIOUR OF THERMALLY CYCLED SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED Mg ALLOYS

Jens Kiehn, Carola Köhler and Karl Ulrich Kainer
Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik
Technische Universität Clausthal, D-38678 Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the thermal stability of the δ -Al₂O₃ short fibre reinforced alloys AZ91 and QE22 produced by the squeeze infiltration process with a fibre volume fraction of 22%. To investigate the course of events inside the MMC during thermal exposition means of dilatometric-, hardness- and stress relaxation measurements, resistometry and electron microscopy have been applied. The relaxation $\Delta\sigma/\sigma=[\sigma(t_1)-\sigma(t_2)]/\sigma(t_1)$ is extremely dependent on the microstructure. The relaxation behaviour of the reinforced and unreinforced alloys in the initial state and after subsequent heat treatments by successive isochronal annealing and thermal cycling in accordance with the time-temperature-profile is described here.

INTRODUCTION

Magnesium metal matrix composites (MMC) aim to enhance strength, stiffness and creep resistance and to keep the low density and good machinability of magnesium alloys. This paper deals with the stress relaxation behaviour and thermal stability of the δ -Al₂O₃ short fibre reinforced AZ91 and QE22 alloys produced by the squeeze infiltration process. The fibre volume fraction was kept at 22%. Fibre preforms showing planar isotropical fibre distribution were used. Specimens for the investigations were taken parallel to the reinforcement plane and solution heat treated.

Cooling of metal matrix composites (MMC) from solidification temperature to room temperature causes internal stresses due to the difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (Δ CTE) of the MMC components. Thermal stresses above proof stress lead to plastic deformation in the absence of external forces. Increased temperature decreases the yield point and accelerates creep and stress relaxation of the matrix. For this reason the plastic deformation depends on the time-temperature-profile that is applied to the MMC. It is shown that cold working due to thermal cycling (proven by microhardness measurements) leads to a saturation in the dimensional changes after a specific number of cycles in contrast to CP-Mg composites, which have a high recovery capability during the high temperature intervals of the time-temperature-profile. For structural applications the dimensional changes have to be taken into account.

The change of the residual resistance ratio of thermally cycled specimen characterizes the precipitation behaviour but is not able to resolve the creation and annihilation of dislocations due

to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients (ΔCTE) or recovery at the upper temperature. The relaxation $\Delta\sigma/\sigma=[\sigma(t_1)-\sigma(t_2)]/\sigma(t_1)$ is extremely dependent on the microstructure which is proven in experiments with unreinforced specimens in as-cast and heat treated conditions. Defects such as inclusions, voids, dislocations, boundaries and matrix fibre interfaces influence internal friction and contribute to the relaxation phenomena.

In the present work reversible stress relaxation measurement is presented as a powerful means in the analysis of the thermal stability of the thermally cycled magnesium alloys AZ91 and QE22.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The production of the Mg-MMC by squeeze casting is schematically shown in Figure 1 [1]. The preforms consist mainly of $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short fibres (Saffil[®], ICI \rightarrow 96-97% Al_2O_3 , 4-3% SiO_2) and a binder containing Al_2O_3 and starch. The production of the preforms in layers leads to a planar isotropical fibre distribution. Preheating of the preforms to a temperature higher than the temperature of the melt avoids solidification beginning at the fibres during the melt-infiltration. Additionally, the starch is driven out of the preform. The pressure for forcing the melt into the preform is applied in two steps to prevent compression of the preform. The second step, with an increased pressure of $\approx 130\text{MPa}$, closes pores and shrinkage cavities. One of the advantages of the squeeze casting technology in comparison to PM-production routes is the short time of contact between the liquid metal and the fibres. Only a slight reaction between the fibre and the matrix can

Figure 1. Flow chart of the squeeze casting technology [1].

be observed resulting in occasional reaction products and precipitates. Composite materials consisting of AZ91 or QE22 matrix and 22vol.% $\delta\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ short fibre reinforcement were produced by squeeze-casting. Mg_2Si and $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ are found at the matrix-fibre-interface due to reactions of the melt with the Saffil-fibre and/or the binder. Diffractometer phase analysis gave some evidence for the occurrence of MgO . The AZ91 (nominal composition 9wt%Al, 1wt%Zn, 0.2wt%Mn) alloy solidifies as a degenerated eutecticum. $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$ precipitates as fine and coarse particles from the $\alpha\text{-Mg}$ solid solution. At the matrix- fibre-interface Mg_2Si is again found. The as-cast QE22 (nominal composition 2.5wt%Ag, 2wt%Nd, 0.6wt%Zr) specimens show $\alpha\text{-Mg}$ solid solution with big precipitates containing Ag and rare earth preferentially situated at the matrix-fibre-interface and the grain boundaries. There is a difference in microstructure between MMC's and the unreinforced material. Coarse grains with columnar structure are found in the

MMC's in contrast to equiaxed grains in the unreinforced area. The fibres do not act as heterogeneous nuclei due to the high preform temperature [2,3]. The T6 heat treatment (solution annealing followed by artificially ageing) encourages Mg_2Si and $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ precipitates found in the as cast condition to redissolve. The eutecticum in AZ91 is new formatted to alternating lamellas of α -Mg solid solution and $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$. In QE22, fine precipitates are also found situated at twin- and grain boundaries. [4]

Figure 2 shows schematically the experimental setup for the reversible stress relaxation

Figure 2. Experimental setup for the measurement of the reversible stress relaxation using an electrodynamic balance.

measurement with electrodynamic balances. A detailed description is given elsewhere [5,6]. The temperature of the experimental setup is kept constant to $20^{\circ}C \pm 0.1^{\circ}C$. Because of the shape of the specimen bar, fixed with one end in the specimen holder, the bar acts as a soft spring. A weight is put on the free end and lies simultaneously on the scale of the balance. The scale is lifted or lowered electromagnetically (Z') and thus a constant strain can be applied to the specimen. The occurring stress relaxation $\Delta\sigma/\sigma = [\sigma(t_1) - \sigma(t_2)]/\sigma(t_1)$ after the loading causes a change in the weight reading, which is continuously recorded by a PC. The total applied stress is about 5% of the proof stress of the chosen alloys. Assuming a linear time dependence for the irreversible stress relaxation it is possible to separate reversible and irreversible stress relaxation by the evaluation of subsequent measurements with lifted and lowered sample bar. After the subtraction of the balance relaxation which occurs without sample, just with the weight on the scale, the reversible stress relaxation can be calculated:

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} = \frac{\Delta E}{E} = \frac{\Delta G}{G} = \frac{G(t_1) - G(t_2)}{G(t_1)} \quad (1)$$

E is the Young's modulus, G the shear modulus. The stress relaxation $\Delta\sigma/\sigma$ was determined over the time period $t_1=3s$ to $t_2=3030s$.

The composite materials consisting of AZ91 or QE22 matrix and 22vol% δ - Al_2O_3 short fibre reinforcement were solution heat treated followed by an artificial ageing (T6). Specimens for stress relaxation and dilatometric measurements were taken parallel to the planes of isotropically distributed fibres. The specimens were thermally cycled between room temperature and $300^{\circ}C$ with time intervals of 15min cooling and 15min heating. Solution heat treated samples (T4) were heat treated for 15min in successive isochronal steps of $20^{\circ}C$ up to $300^{\circ}C$ to evaluate the precipitation behaviour in the first thermal cycle. All treatments have been also performed with unreinforced specimens. Since the microstructure of thermomechanically treated magnesium alloys is even sensitive to ageing at room temperature the specimen were stored in liquid nitrogen and the period of measurement and handling at room temperature was always the same. The

determination of the stress relaxation (2 measurements à 353.5min) took about 12 hours and afterwards the Vickers hardness HV10 was measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the emphasized influence of the thermal cycling between room temperature and 300°C for the reinforced QE22 alloy. Also remarkable is the drop in the relaxation strength after 6 hours (of measurement) at room temperature for the thermally cycled bending sample. The time dependence of the stress relaxation for all specimens is similar to that shown in Figure 3 and can be described by a power law of the type shown in equation 2. N is the area density of dislocation segments and $\langle l \rangle$ the mean segment length:

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} = \frac{\Delta E}{E} = N\langle l \rangle^2 B(t^n - t_0^n)e^{-nU_0/kT} \tag{2}$$

Such a time dependence of stress relaxation without any pronounced step is caused by a wide spectrum of relaxation times indicating a dislocation mechanism.

Figure 3. Change of relative modulus versus time in logarithmical scale measured at 20°C in different treatments (T6=solution heat treated and artificially aged; additional 100 cycles between room temperature and 300°C) and in two time intervals (1st to 6th h and 7th to 12th h).

Figure 4 shows the dependence of the relaxation strength $\Delta E/E$ after 3030s (determined from the mean value of 6 measurements between the 6th and 12th hour after the treatment) and Vickers hardness HV10 of short fibre reinforced QE22 on the number of cycles between room temperature and 300°C. In contrast to the unreinforced samples that have been comparably measured, reinforced QE22 shows an increase of relaxation strength and a contrary decrease of hardness. Relaxation and hardness peaks are in good correspondence. The investigation of the deformation of Saffil short fibre reinforced QE22 by means of dilatometric measurements [7] (samples of the same cast and heat treatment as the samples described in the present paper) due to

thermal cycling shows a steady rise of the specimen-length up to 15 cycles. Afterwards no ongoing elongation is found. This saturation is explained by work hardening due to thermal cycling of the composite with components exhibiting different thermal expansion. For the mentioned plastic deformation in the first cycles dislocations should be mobilized or generated. Therefore, the increase in relaxation strength in Figure 4 indicates the dominating effect of dislocation generation in the first cycles. The decrease in the subsequent cycles can be explained by dislocation pinning. The unreinforced sample shows a decrease in relaxation strength and hardness. The drop in hardness in the reinforced and unreinforced specimen is about 30 Vickers units and can be explained by ageing effects. Particles containing Mg, Ag and Nd of small ($\approx 100\text{nm}$) and medium size ($\approx 0.6\mu\text{m}$) have been found by means of transmission electron microscopy in both, reinforced and unreinforced QE22, and large grain boundary particles in unreinforced QE22 after 10 cycles between room temperature and 300°C . The resistivity measurements indicate that the precipitation predominantly takes place in the first cycles. The slight increase in relaxation strength after 500 cycles could be a sign for a damage of the fibre e.g. by the solution of fibre atoms within the matrix.

Figure 4. Dependence of relaxation strength $\Delta E/E$ after 3030s (determined from the mean value of 6 measurements between the 6th and 12th h after the treatment) and Vickers hardness HV10 of reinforced QE22. The initial state was solution treated and artificially aged (T6). Subsequently the specimens were thermally cycled between room temperature and 300°C (15min cooling, 15min heating).

In Figure 5 the reversible stress relaxation and the Vickers hardness of reinforced and unreinforced QE22 are plotted versus the temperature of successive isochronal annealing (15min in steps of 20°C). Again the contribution of the fibre matrix interface improves the relaxation strength of the reinforced sample. Three stages can be differentiated for reinforced QE22. After the rise from the initial value the relaxation remains on a plateau up to 100°C . The decline of the relaxation strength starting at about $T_a=100^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds well with resistivity measurements. At 220°C the relaxation starts to rise again. The relaxation peak of the unreinforced QE22 is accompanied by a continuous rise of the hardness. To understand the relaxation and hardness development of the reinforced specimen extensive transmission electron microscopy investigations have to be performed.

Figure 5. Reversible stress relaxation $\Delta E/E$ after 3030s and Vickers hardness HV10 of reinforced and unreinforced QE22 versus temperature of step by step annealing (15min in steps of 20°C). The initial state was solution treated (T4).

Figure 6. Reversible stress relaxation $\Delta E/E$ after 3030s and Vickers hardness HV10 of reinforced and unreinforced AZ91 versus temperature of step by step annealing (15min in steps of 20°C). The initial state was solution treated (T4).

Figure 7. Dependence of relaxation strength $\Delta E/E$ after 3030s (determined from the mean value of 6 measurements between the 6th and 12th h after the treatment) and Vickers hardness HV10 of reinforced and unreinforced AZ91. The initial state was solution treated and artificially aged (T6). Subsequently the specimens were thermally cycled between room temperature and 300°C (15min cooling, 15min heating).

Figure 6 and Figure 7 give a general idea of the reversible stress relaxation behaviour of AZ91. The samples were treated simultaneously and in the same way as the QE22 specimens discussed above. In contradiction to the situation in Figure 4, where reinforced QE22 shows a rise in the relaxation strength up to 100 cycles and a decline of the hardness, reinforced AZ91 as well as unreinforced AZ91 reveals a decrease in relaxation strength and hardness. The initial value of the relaxation of reinforced AZ91 is approximately twice as high as the initial value of reinforced QE22. The distinct drop from the initial value may be a reason that an increase due to dislocation generation as a result of ΔCTE , as mentioned above for reinforced QE22, can not be resolved. Figure 6 exposes the good accordance of hardness and relaxation for unreinforced AZ91. A peak in hardness and relaxation strength for solution treated unreinforced AZ91 at approximately 250°C, as shown here, was reported before in [8]. The Vickers hardness HV10 represents a mean value of the fibre and the matrix hardness. The fibre hardness (and the strength of the fibre-matrix-interface) seems not to be affected by the successive isochronal annealing and for this reason changes in the matrix hardness (if they occur) are not very well resolved for the reinforced AZ91 and QE22 specimens in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Nevertheless the stress relaxation $(\Delta E/E) \cdot 1000$ after 3030s shows pronounced changes. Between 100°C and 160°C a monotonous increase of the relaxation strength of about 30% is found for reinforced AZ91 and a slow decrease follows afterwards. Both, reinforced and unreinforced specimens show an increase of relaxation strength after $T_a=280^\circ\text{C}$ that deviates from the hardness (Figure 6).

SUMMARY

Reversible stress relaxation measurements have been introduced to investigate the effects of thermal cycling on magnesium MMC's, especially dislocation generation due to the mismatch of the thermal expansion coefficients (ΔCTE). The reinforced QE22 magnesium alloy shows an increase of the relaxation strength within the first 100 cycles that can be explained by ΔCTE . Reversible stress relaxation measurements after successive isochronal annealing show good correspondence with hardness and resistivity measurements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the *Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft*.

REFERENCES

1. K.U. Kainer, Herstellung und Eigenschaften von faserverstärkten Magnesiumverbundwerkstoffen. *Metallische Verbundwerkstoffe* ed. by K.U. Kainer, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Oberursel, 219-244 (1994).
2. K.U. Kainer, 12th *Riso Int. Symp. on Materials Science* ed. by N. Hansen, National Laboratory Roskilde, 429-434 (1991).
3. K.U. Kainer, Cast Magnesium Alloys Reinforced by Short Fibres. *Magnesium Alloys and Their Applications* ed. by B.L. Mordike and F. Hehmann, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Oberursel, 415-422 (1993).
4. C. Köhler, *Thermische Beständigkeit von Kurzfaserverstärkten Magnesium Al_2O_3 -Verbundwerkstoffen*, PhD-Thesis TU Clausthal (1994).
5. W. Riehemann, P. Fleischer, and V. Martens, High resolution measurement of stress relaxation in engineering materials with an electrodynamic balance. *Technisches Messen* **59**, 245-251(1992)
6. P. Buchhagen, W. Riehemann, and B.L. Mordike, Reversible Stress Relaxation of Saffil Fibre Reinforced AZ91. *Magnesium Alloys and Their Applications* ed. by B.L. Mordike and F. Hehmann, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Oberursel, 455-460 (1993).
7. J. Kiehn, C. Köhler, K.U. Kainer, 6th *Int. Symp. on Plasticity of Metals and Alloys* ed. by P. Lukác, Prague (1994) in press.
8. P. Buchhagen, W. Riehemann, and B.L. Mordike, Stress Relaxation and Damping Capacity of Magnesium and Magnesium Alloys. *Magnesium Alloys and Their Applications* ed. by B.L. Mordike and F. Hehmann, DGM Informationsgesellschaft, Oberursel, 229-236 (1993).